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Future Developments in Silicon Chemistry—An Industrial Perspective

Barry Arkles

Gelest Inc., 612 William Leigh Drive, Tullytown, PA 19007-6308, USA

I've been asked to take an industrial perspective on promising research in silicon chemistry. This means reviewing current research for trends that can lead to future developments that are not only good science, but can have an impact on silicon technology and the growth of the industry. It is important to emphasize that the role of research is not only to make new discoveries, but to develop a framework of knowledge that allows researchers to be both receptive and responsive to discoveries that come from outside their field of inquiry. Discovery from outside the area of silicon technology frequently impacts silicon research. Predicting which directions of research will be fruitful

is usually a fruitless task. Even so, industry must "bet" on which efforts to support. Despite the odds being against predictions of this type, I am confident that at least some of the areas I describe will become important.

THE PRESENT

It is useful to review the state of the industry in order to see the current trends in growth. The bulk of silicon technology can be divided into five main product areas which developed from hydrogen chloride and methyl chloride direct reactions with silicon.

The silicone area is dominant, comprising \$5.0–5.5 x 10⁹ of overall sales of primary silicon containing products. An approximate market share is presented in the following table.

1992 Worldwide Silicone and Silane Sales
(in millions of dollars)

Dow Corning*	1,850
General Electric*	750
Shin-Etsu*	700
Wacker	700
Rhone-Poulenc	500
Bayer/Miles	350
OSi/former Union Carbide*	325
Hüls/Nünschritz/Petrarch	175
All Others (includes Toray*, Toshiba*, Tonen*, Goldschmidt, Chisso, Ethyl, Degussa, Allied, PCR, CIS/former USSR)	650
TOTAL	6000

*includes allocated share of joint ventures

Historically, silicones grew at rates in excess of three times that of the overall economy. In the '90s, this growth slowed and approached a rate two times that of the overall economy. While this can still be considered a healthy growth rate, the rate has become more dependent on factors which are not

“discovery” dependent. These factors include greater efficiencies in production based on improved selectivity, reduced waste and economy of scale, expanded distribution of existing products enabling them to reach a greater number of appropriate industrial and consumer applications, and form-change distribution in which existing products are supplied in forms that are “user friendly.” Examples of “user friendly” forms of silicones are water-based emulsions and concentrates in thermoplastics. Growth beyond 2X is likely to depend both on “discovery” and litigation trends in which the excellent environmental and safety record of silicones allows them to replace less-safe products. A significant portion of the growth of the late '70s and early '80s was based on the “discovery” that cyclic siloxanes were excellent cosmetic vehicles for antiperspirant formulations and litigation which forced chlorinated biphenyls out of dielectric applications and allowed in more expensive silicones.

Organosilanes sold outside the silicone industry have revenues 5–7% that of silicones. The growth rate of organosilanes is about 3/4 that of silicones. There are two main classes of organosilanes: 1) the organic substitution is non-functional, e.g., unsubstituted aliphatic or aromatic, comprising 30% of the silicon chemical market; or 2) the substitution is functional, e.g., amino or methacrylate functional silanes, comprising 65% of the silicon chemical market. The remaining 5% of the market includes silicate esters and chlorosilanes. The uses of organosilanes are shown below.

NON-FUNCTIONAL SILANE MARKETS

FUNCTIONAL SILANE MARKETS

Ironically, it should be noted that despite the generation of many new functional silanes, for the last five years, the growth of non-functional silanes has outpaced the growth of functional silanes. The growth of non-functional silanes is being driven by architectural coatings and high efficiency-supported polyolefin polymerization. From technical and industrial perspectives, however, organosilanes which are intermediates and modifiers of silicones have interest and importance at least as great as silanes sold for applications other than silicones.

THE FUTURE Silicon Bond Formation by Catalytic Processes

Efficient methods for bond formation were critical in the development of silicon technology. The unique properties of silicones were recognized by early investigators, such as F. Hyde, but the lack of cost-effective methods to produce intermediates limited applications. The explosive growth of silicones was facilitated by E. Rochow, R. Müller, L. Sommer and J. Speier. Similarly, the utility of a wide range of other polymers, principally polysilanes and polysilazanes, were

recognized and explored by R. West and D. Seyferth, but efficient methods of producing these materials have not been realized. New silicon bond formation processes have been discovered that lead to these polymers, but to date they have not enabled the technology due to limitations, not only in their efficiency and selectivity, but in the lack of silicon hydride intermediates.

A catalytic reaction that leads to a variety of polymeric building blocks is the metathesis reaction of vinyl silanes. The reaction employs a ruthenium based catalyst system which may mediate other reactions for silane functional olefins. Enabling technology is required to improve selectivity and efficiency of this reaction. The vinylsilanes required for this reaction are also derived from silicon hydride intermediates.

The development of new high efficiency routes to organosilicon hydrides and organosilicon dihydrides is essential to achieve utility for these reactions and marks a clear research and technological opportunity. Possible solutions are hydrogen promoted direct process reactions for methylhydrosilanes, such as those described by K. Lewis [5], and high yield disproportionation reactions of the type first reported by M. Kumada.

Siloxane and Silicate Assembly

Accepting for the moment that the future, like the present of silicon technology, will be dependent on siloxane chemistry, greater understanding of processes which lead to the assembly of siloxanes and silicates from simple intermediates, particularly in aqueous environments, may be the key to future developments. Self-assembly of silicates and silsesquioxanes

in aqueous regimes appear to be likely candidates for future investigation. The outcome could include practical routes to sol-gel derived silicates, organic modified silicates (ORMOSILS) [6], resins and resinous reinforcement. Understanding of the hydrolytic behavior of the silane esters was recently extended by B. Arkles [7] and E. Pohl [8]. The early work of J. Brown, which modeled the assembly of monoalkylsilanes, has been superseded and elegantly

supplemented in studies by W. Klemperer [9] and F. Feher [10]. The impact of this work on practical silicone chemistry is apparent from the work of J. Wengrovius in which the structure of "Q" reinforcing resins, essential components of pressure sensitive adhesives and for clear high strength silicones, was proposed as an oligomeric chain of silicate cubes [11].

Wengrovius—MQ Resins as Substituted Polymeric Cubes $[M_{0.625}Q^{OH}_{0.188}Q_{0.812}]_{32}$

A further elaboration that opens a new avenue is the work of A. Bassindale on "octopus" silsesquioxanes [12].

One of the incongruous facts in silicon technology is that relatively little is understood about the behavior of simple water soluble silicates. In neutral water, the silicates are soluble to the extent of 70–120 ppm and are in equilibrium with silicic acid $Si(OH)_4$, a monomeric form of silica. Silicic acid is involved in both mineralization and biomineralization of complex structures. Approximately 10% of the dry weight of all living organisms is mineral structure. The overwhelming biomineralization process is silicification, exemplified by diatoms which represent 20–25% of the world's primary biomass production and perform the bulk of mineralization for the global biomass. Recently, B. Volcani and M. Hildebrand [13] have demonstrated that approximately 30 genes

are turned on and off by the presence of silicates in diatoms. This work may lead to our first insights into the biotransformation of silicates and methods for the controlled assembly of amorphous silica structures.

Higher Order Silicon Structures

Control of the topology at secondary and tertiary levels is an extremely promising area for the development of processable structural materials. Silicon polymer chemistry has precedents for most of the techniques employed in the synthesis of organic polymers, but there has not been sufficient elaboration of this technology to allow practical preparation of materials with utility. The work reported to date undoubtedly represents important first steps. A few examples follow.

Ring Assembly: Fusion of cyclosilazane rings, directly and via borazine linkages (D. Seyferth) [14, 15].

Dendrimers: K. Matyjaszewski (polysilane); A. van der Made (polysilylalkylene) [16].

Tube and Sheet Structures: M. Kenney [17].

Postulated tube alkoxide idealized by the omission of intratube and intertube crosslinks where R is *n*-Pr, Me and H.

An objective of microelectronic and optoelectronic technology, silicon-based light-emitting diodes, now appears within grasp with the observation of porous partially oxidized silica [18, 19]. It is

interesting to consider whether a synthetic polymer technology built from polysilane-polysilicate materials could yield a molecularly engineered rather than an etch-fabrication approach to these structures.

Oxidation of porous silicon nanostructures. Photoluminescence is observed in structures a-c; electroluminescence in structures a-b.

Chiral Amplification

The role of organosilanes in synthesis has been dominated by their behavior as “bulky protons.” The use of silanes as “bulky asymmetric protons” can be traced to the early work of L. Sommer. While intermittent reports by G. Larson [20] and others have promoted the asymmetric effects of silanes on synthesis, the application of these materials has only recently become of extreme interest in chiral drug design and in optoelectronic technology where device “sidedness” and the interaction of light has become important for display devices [21].

Silicon in Non-Traditional Coordination States

The extension of organosilicon chemistry to higher and lower coordination states is an opening to new bond forming reactions. The work of P. Jutzi [22] with pentamethylcyclopentadienyl ligands demonstrates that the +2 state of silicon, like its isosteres germanium, tin, and lead is accessible. Significant advances in commercial organo-tin technology were achieved by exploitation of short-lived +2 intermediates produced from tin metal [23] and it is possible that analogous chemistry could be developed for silicon.

Work in hypercoordinate silicon has been revived by R. Corriu [24]. New classes of structure and reactivity, exemplified by the hydrosilicates, have been demonstrated for the penta- and hexacoordinate states of silicon. At the Xth International Silicon Symposium held in Poznan late last year, octacoordinate Si was proposed for the first time. It is also interesting to note that recent advances in geochemistry, in which silicon in the hexacoordinate state in the earth's mantle was found, play an active role in silicate formation.

Conclusion

The areas in which I've anticipated opportunities for growth of silicon science and technology, described only from a parochial viewpoint, are extremely positive. With only a modest amount of "discovery," growth well in excess of twice that of the economy should be sustainable. There were many exciting reports from the Poznan conference—West's stable Si=C=C and silylated fullerene, Tokitoh's stable Si=S, Ando's and Barton's 6-, 7- and 8-membered rings with -Si-C=C-, among others. While it is difficult to anticipate the utility of this work at this time, they may provide the keys to new areas. The strong basic science of silicon developed by researchers and their receptiveness to discovery in different fields will continue to be propellants for growth. ❖

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The original version of this overview will be published by Gordon and Breach in the book *Progress in Organosilicon Chemistry*, edited by Bogdan Marciniak and Julian Chojnowski, and which is due out in the fall.

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